

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH IN CHILDREN OF PRIMARY PRESCHOOL AGE

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Summary: The article is devoted to the importance of the development of speech of preschoolers, the features of development, pedagogical methods and techniques used in preschool institutions when teachers work with children of preschool age are considered.

Key words: speech, speech development, pedagogical activity, methods, technologies.

One of the most important indicators of the level of formation of the intellectual potential of the child is the richness of his speech, therefore, it is important for us, educators, to support and ensure the development of the mental and speech capabilities of preschoolers. Ensuring the systematic development of speech skills and cognitive activity is one of the functions of a preschool teacher. The more competent the speech, the better the active vocabulary is developed, the more actively the child seeks to learn about the world around him, which helps him develop and learn something new. Consequently, mental cognitive processes - attention, memory, thinking - improve faster.

For the speech of the baby to improve, favorable conditions are necessary. Speech is the main social function, but biological prerequisites for its full development are not enough. The need for verbal communication is developed in life practice and directly depends on the interaction of the child with the social development of the child's speech. The leading role is occupied by adults: parents and kindergarten teachers. From the culture of speech of adults and how they talk to the

child, how much time they devote to verbal communication and the success of the baby in learning the language depends.

Of great importance for the development of a child's speech is the living environment in which he is brought up, the attitude of surrounding adults, care, educational influences and the child's own activity in various activities. The development of the speech of preschool children takes place in several stages, at each of them the child acquires new skills and becomes one step higher in the use of the word. At the age of 3-4 years, children are already actively speaking. At this time, speech activity increases, a vocabulary of words is acquired, speech reasoning lengthens and becomes more complicated, eventually turning into stories, their grammatical design progresses, the role of speech as a means of regulating behavior increases, and a sound culture of speech begins to form.

For the development of the speech of preschool children, it is necessary to create a certain subject-speech environment that will contribute to the formation of not only correct, but also good oral speech. Speech development proceeds more successfully in a favorable speech environment. In the program of preschool education, there are a large number of techniques and methods that teachers use in their activities. The main traditional technologies that are widely used in preschool organizations include visual, verbal, game, indirect methods. The development of speech is a multifaceted, systematic and productive pedagogical activity, which involves the use of a large supply of special methodological techniques and speech exercises for children, which contribute to the expansion of children's vocabulary, develop sound culture and the grammatical structure of speech, coherent (monologue and dialogic) and figurative speech.. It is important to keep in mind that each child is unique and has its own individual pace of development. In a preschool organization, educators organize a variety of game situations - looking at pictures, toys, compiling descriptive stories, reading fairy tales and stories, learning poems.

Their goal is to teach children to compose their stories, play out fairy tales, be able to ask questions and retell the content they heard, and compose their own story based on the content they heard. At preschool age, play occupies a special place, and

it is through it that the child learns to communicate not only with his peers, but also with adults. Communication situations most often arise spontaneously at the initiative of a child or an adult, while teachers see and support such situations, trying to catch the meaning of the child's statement, which often consists of one or two short phrases, at this moment it is important to encourage the baby to dialogue or a fuller statement, asking leading questions.

Analyzing the experience of teachers, it can be noted that generally accepted methods are not always effective in working with modern preschoolers. When dealing with children, it is important to make the most of all the techniques and methods known in pedagogy, including modern approaches that improve mental and cognitive abilities, develop the lexical and grammatical structure and coherent speech of preschoolers. Innovative technologies for the development of speech of preschool children mean innovations in the content, forms, methods, means of pedagogical activity, which reflect the latest research and achievements of advanced pedagogical experience: ICT technologies, logorhythmics, mnemonic tables, design method, modeling, pedagogical art. therapy, etc.

Pedagogical innovations help to improve the processes of education and training, combining progressive creative technologies and stereotyped elements of education that have proven their effectiveness in the process of pedagogical activity. Another very important condition for the development of children's speech is the close interaction of educators with the parents of pupils. It is very important that parents and educators be like-minded in solving the most important task of speech development of children, since the child learns the experience of verbal communication from others, therefore it is very important that parents, when talking with children, monitor their pronunciation, clearly pronounce words and sounds. Using in our work a variety of methods, techniques, technologies for the speech development of pupils of our group of middle preschool age, speech improves by the end of the school year, it becomes much more diverse, more accurate and richer in content.

The concentration of attention to the speech of others increases, our pupils are able to listen to the answers of adults to the end. They have a well-formed imitation skill, which is expressed in the ability to reproduce movements, actions, words and simple phrases after an adult. Speech development, in our opinion, is one of the most important educational areas. Undoubtedly, other areas are no less important, but the full development of children in any of these educational areas is not possible without speech, without communication, without communicative activity. Summing up, we want to say that our common single task is to raise a diversified healthy child.

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